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Biochemical effects and molluscicidal activity of some vegetable oils against adults of land snails

Salwa, A. E. Abd-El-Haleem¹; Farag, M. F. N. G.¹; Hend, A. El Nasharty²; Dewidar, A. A.³; Mohamed, G. Salama¹; Hend, Mohamed Abd-Elmonem¹; Eman, M. Ghareeb¹, Eman, M. Elgohary¹ and Rania, I. M. Almoselhy⁴

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Plant Protection Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Zagazig University, Zagazig, Egypt.

³Horticulture Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

⁴Oils and Fats Research Department, Food Technology Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the molluscicidal activity of some vegetable oils against adults of land snails. Three oil treatments were investigated: Fresh oil (FO), a blend of sunflower and soybean seeds mixed in a 1:1 ratio, a waste cooking oil (WCO) blend of used sunflower and soybean in the same ratio, and lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO). These treatments were tested against adults of *Monacha cartusiana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropod: Hygromiidae), *Eobania vermiculata* (O. F. Müller) and *Theba pisana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropod: Helicidae) snails at concentrations of 7.5, 15, and 30%, respectively, under laboratory conditions. The results revealed that mortality percentages increased with concentration, the highest impact observed at a concentration of 30%. *M. cartusiana* exhibited the greatest susceptibility, with mortality percentages of 20.00%, 26.67%, and 66.67%, while *E. vermiculata* showed the lowest sensitivity, and observed with 13.33%, 20.00%, and 26.67% for FO, WCO, and LGVO, respectively after 28 days of treatment. Biochemical investigations demonstrated a significant impact on enzyme activity. WCO treatment caused a reduction in amylase and invertase activities in all species, indicating metabolic disruption. Conversely, LGVO resulted in increased enzyme activity, suggesting physiological stress responses. In *M. cartusiana*, WCO reduced amylase and invertase activities by up to -11.58% and -19.99%, respectively, while LGVO increased them by up to 27.04% and 9.71% at 7 days of treatment. Finally, the tested oils can be categorized in decreasing order of effectiveness as LGVO > WCO > FO. The differential susceptibility among snail species may be attributed to variations in body size and physiological characteristics.

Introduction

Terrestrial gastropods such as land snails have grown in significance and become significant pests because they harm a variety of plants, including field crops, fruit trees, vegetables, and decorative plants all over the world (Barker, 2002 and Badrawy *et al.*, 2024). They attack plant leaves, tubers, and roots. These snails are far more destructive now than they were in the past because of the increased density and speed of traffic and transportation, which allows them to move freely not just across nations but also between regions. A foul stench released by snail intra-field travel deters and even prevents animals and humans from eating these infected plants (Ismail *et al.*, 2017; Bayoumi, 2018; Abd El-Haleem, 2021 and Abd El-Haleim *et al.*, 2022). Synthetic molluscicides are essential for controlling land mollusks, one of the most destructive agricultural pests worldwide (Ali and Abou El-Atta, 2023). They are hazardous to other creatures in the environment, are the basis for chemical control (Thiengo *et al.*, 2007). Unluckily, the environment and human health suffer as a result of farmers' haphazard and negligent application of pesticides. In addition to these disadvantages, chemical treatment is a time-consuming and insufficiently effective process (Chen *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, we will inevitably discover a different natural bio-control agent. Several attempts have been made by writers to examine the effect of natural compounds on snails, e.g., Aal and Hamed (2010) on *Eobania vermiculata* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropod:Helicidae) and *Monacha cartusiana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropod:Hygromiidae), Abd El-Aal *et al.* (2024) on *E. vermiculata* and Farag *et al.* (2025a) on *Theba pisana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropod:Helicidae) and *E. vermiculata*. So, using natural

molluscicides, including botanical oils, is seen to be the most effective method of controlling snails (Singh and Singh, 2004; Gabr *et al.*, 2006; Farag, 2012; Farag and Sabry, 2017; Edyta *et al.*, 2018; Abdel-Rahman, 2020; Ali and Abou El-Atta, 2023; Farag *et al.*, 2024 and Farag *et al.*, 2025b). A blend of used sunflower and soybean oils (UO) from several restaurants in a 1:1 ratio offers serious health hazards, such as cancer, heart disease, and neurological diseases, as well as environmental problems when improperly disposed of responsibly (Farag *et al.*, 2024). Thus, the goal of this work was to use UO as a molluscicidal. The ease of use, high bioactive potential, and economic feasibility of molluscicides derived from plants, such as essential oils, made them convenient (Wicht *et al.*, 2004 and Ali and Abou El-Atta, 2023). Therefore, it is essential to develop environmentally friendly substitutes for conventional molluscicides. So, the purpose of this investigation was to ascertain the molluscicidal activity of some botanical oils against adult land snails of the species *M. cartusiana*, *T. pisana*, and *E. vermiculata*.

Materials and methods

1. Materials:

1.1. Chemicals and reagents:

All solvents and chemicals used in the study were of analytical and HPLC grade obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, USA.

1.2. Tested land snails:

Adults of the glassy clover snail, *M. cartusiana*, were taken from wheat fields in the Sheeba site, Zagazig district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. While adults of two snail species, the brown garden snail *E. vermiculata*, and the white garden snail *T. pisana*, were gathered from an orchard that was growing navel oranges, *Citrus sinensis* L., in the Menia El-Kamh region of the Sharkia Governorate in Egypt and

identified using the keys provided by Godan (1983). A glass terrarium with damp clay soil that was 75% full of water was utilized to host healthy and comparable individuals. Before the snails received the acclimatization therapy, they were fed fresh green cabbage leaves every day for two weeks (El-Okda, 1981).

1.3. Tested oils:

The first was an oil mixture that was bought from Afco Misr Ataqa firm in Suez city, Suez governorate, Egypt. It contained fresh sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) and soybean (*Glycine max* L.) oils mixed in a 1:1 ratio (FO). The second was a blend of waste cooking oil (WCO) from used sunflower and soybean oils collected from several restaurants in Zagazig city, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt, in a 1:1 ratio. The oil was stored at 5 °C until analysis after it was filtered and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The third was lemon grass volatile oil (*Cymbopogon citratus*) (LGVO), which was brought from the Medicinal and Aromatic Plants Research and Reproduction Department, Horticulture Research Institute (HRI), Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Egypt.

2. Methods:

2.1. Spraying technique of tested snails:

Using a spraying technique, snails and cabbage leaves were treated with the evaluated vegetable oils (FO, WCO, and LGVO) at concentrations of 7.5, 15 and 30% which were selected from initial testing. To prepare concentrations, 30 ml of each oil item were mixed with 69.75 ml of sterile water and 0.25 milliliters of 30% tween 80. These solutions were further diluted to obtain between 15 and 7.5% for each tested oil. For each concentration, 15 healthy snails were placed in plastic boxes (0.75 kg, capacity) for three replicates. Cups were covered with muslin cloth and secured with rubber

bands to prevent escape (Hilmy and Hegab, 2010). For 28 days, untreated leaves were added daily to the treated leaves two days after exposure. To monitor mortality, snails were tapped regularly with a stainless-steel needle for 24 hrs. following treatment. Animal death was defined as loss of reaction, as described by Abdel-Rahman (2020). Dead snails were counted and removed as soon as identified. Mortality rates were recorded after 1, 3, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days of treatment. For the control, fresh cabbage leaves were spraying utilizing compound-free water and corrected utilizing Abbott's formula (1925).

2.2. Analytical technique:

2.2.1. Chemical parameters of tested oils:

Peroxide value (PV) was determined according to the method outlined in A.O.A.C. (2016), whereas acidity was determined according to the methods described in PN-ISO 660 (2020).

2.2.2. Analysis of the tested oils using gas chromatography (GC):

The GC analysis of Lemon grass volatile oil was carried out using the gas chromatography equipment that met the following requirements: A flame ionization detector is included with the DsChrom 6200 Gas Chromatograph. Column: BPX-5, 30m x 0.25mm ID x 0.25µm film, 5% phenyl (equiv.) polysilphenylene-siloxane 1µl is the sample size. The temperature program ramps up from 70°C to 200°C at a rate of 10°C /minute. 280 °C is the detector temperature (FID). Gas carrier: nitrogen. The flow rates are 300 ml/min for air, 30 ml/min for H₂, and 30 ml/min for N₂. The main components of the tested volatile oils were identified by contrasting their retention durations with those of the actual samples injected under the same conditions. Each compound's relative fraction was calculated using the area of the peak that matched it. The gas

chromatography analysis was carried out by the medicinal and aromatic plants research department laboratory at the horticulture research institute (Farak and Sakla, 2019). While fatty acid composition of FO and WCO samples of tested fixed oils was determined by gas chromatography (GC) according to (PN-ISO 12966-2, 2017).

2.3. Biochemical studies:

Sample preparation:

The soft tissues of the *T. pisana*, *M. cartusiana*, and *E. vermiculata* snails were taken after the shells of the mature mollusks were removed. The tissues were weighted and then homogenized in distilled water at a 1:10 (w/v) ratio as a describe by Abd El-Haleim *et al.* (2006). The homogenates were then centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 minutes at 5°C. The resulting supernatants were promptly analyzed to assess the activity of the amylase and invertase enzymes following the method outlined by Ishaaya and Swiriski (1976).

2.4. Statistical analysis:

The obtained data were subjected to statistical analysis by one-way ANOVA and the least significant difference (LSD) at (P>0.05) (Cohort software, 2005).

Results and discussion

1. Chemical properties such as acidity % and peroxide value of sunflower oil and soybean oil combined in a 1:1 ratio (FO and WCO):

1.1. Acidity % and peroxide value (PV) of WCO and FO oils were studied in Table (1). Acidity % and PV determinations are one of the best indicators of oil harm. Data showed that WCO had a greater acidity percentage

and peroxide value than FO. The acidity and peroxide values of oils were (0.05 & 4.31%) and (6.28 & 18.79 Meq.O₂/Kg) for FO and WCO, respectively. Data agreed with those gained via Kaleem *et al.* (2015), Farag and Sabry (2017), Farag *et al.* (2024), and Elyamani *et al.* (2025).

1.2. Gas chromatography analysis (GC) of the tested vegetable oils:

Following a gas chromatography analysis, the major constituents and percentages of the estimated Lemon grass volatile oil and fixed oils such as FO and WCO are shown in Table (2). The main constituents of Lemon grass oil were geranial (39.23%) and neral (28.78%) Table (2) and Figure (1). For instance, Masamba *et al.* (2003) and Mohamed *et al.* (2012) showed that geranial and neral were the main components of lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO). While the major unsaturated fatty acids in fresh oil (FO) and waste oil (WCO) were linoleic acid C_{18:2} (55.03 and 54.74%), followed by oleic acid C_{18:1} (28.02 and 27.59%), respectively. Among the saturated fatty acids, palmitic acid C_{16:0} had the major percentage (9.12 and 8.77), followed by stearic acid C_{18:0} (3.58 and 3.70%), respectively (Table, 2). Prior research using similar data from Farag and Sabry (2017), Farag *et al.* (2024) and Elyamani *et al.* (2025) reported that the major constituents and percentages of sunflower and soybean oils were linoleic acid, followed by oleic acid of unsaturated fatty acids. While saturated fatty acids, such as palmitic acid that had the major percentage followed by stearic acid.

Table (1): Acidity % and peroxide value of FO and WCO (Sunflower and soybean oils) mixed in a 1:1 ratio (FO and WCO):

Tested oils	Chemical properties	
	Acidity % (as oleic acid)	Peroxide value (Meq.O ₂ /Kg)
FO	0.05	6.28
WCO	4.31	18.79

Fresh oil (FO), Waste cooking oil (WCO).

Table (2): Gas chromatography analysis for tested fixed and volatile oils.

Volatile oil			Fixed oils		
VO				FO	WCO
No.	Component	%	Fatty acids	%	%
1	β -myrcene	12.67	Myristic acid C _{14:0}	0.10	0.09
2	Camphene	0.84	Palmitic acid C _{16:0}	9.12	8.77
3	β -ocimene	0.09	Palmitoleic acid C _{16:1}	0.11	0.10
4	Linalool	1.74	Margaric acid C _{17:0}	0.06	0.06
5	α -terpineol	2.77	Myristoleic acid C _{17:1}	0.03	0.03
6	Isoneral	2.10	Stearic acid C _{18:0}	3.58	3.70
7	Neral	28.78	Oleic acid C _{18:1}	28.02	27.59
8	Geranial	39.23	Linoleic acid C _{18:2}	55.03	54.74
9	Geranyl acetate	3.20	Linolenic acid C _{18:3}	3.11	3.02
10	β -Caryophyllene	2.85	Arachidic acid C _{20:0}	0.24	0.27
11	β -Copaene	1.12	Eicosenic acid C _{20:1}	0.16	0.17
12	Eugenol	0.64	Behenic acid C _{22:0}	0.42	0.47
13	γ -Cadinene	3.97	Total saturated fatty acids	13.52	13.36
	Total	100	Total unsaturated fatty acids	86.46	85.65

Figure (1): Gas chromatography chromatogram for Lemon grass (LGVO) as volatile oil.

2. Toxicological studies:

Impact of tested vegetable oils on adults of *Monacha cartusiana*, *Theba pisana*, and *Eobania vermiculata*, snails after indicated days under laboratory conditions:

The toxic impact of fresh sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) and soybean (*Glycine max*) oils mixed in a 1:1 ratio (FO), sunflower and soybean oils (WCO), and (*Cymbopogon citratus*) (LGVO) against adults of *M. cartusiana*, *T. pisana*, and *E. vermiculata*, snails over a 28-day exposure period by using the spraying technique under laboratory conditions, was summarized in Tables (3, 4 and 5). The data indicated that the accretive mortality percentage increased progressively with longer exposure

time. The lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO) was the most impactful compound on the three species of snails. For *M. cartusiana*, LGVO (30%) led to rise progressively the mortality percentage and reach its maximum at the end of the trial period, whereas achieved the mortality of (40.00%) on the third day then slightly raised to (53.33%) after one week of exposure and reached to maximum impact on 14th day with (66.67%) until the end of trail, in contrast both of FO and WCO had a lesser impact, recording (13.33 & 20.00%), consecutively, at concentration of 30%, then WCO observed a slight increase to (26.67%) over the exposure period from 14 to 28 days as shown in Table (3). At a concentration of 15%, LGVO resulted

in a mortality percentage of (33.33%) after 14, 21, and 28 days of treatment, while WCO had a lower mortality percentage of (20.00%). Notably, at a lower concentration of 7.5 %, both FO and WCO exhibited the same mortality percentage throughout the 28 days, showing values of (0.00 and 6.67%), consecutively. Data in Table (4) demonstrated that LGVO oil gave the utmost impact on the 14th day with a mortality percentage (46.66%) on *T.pisasn* , adults comparable with FO and WCO, which caused their impact with (20.00%) post one week of exposure at a concentration 30%, while on the 21st , WCO gave almost negligible rise with (26.67%). At a concentration of 15% LGVO, a slight efficacy was observed starting from the third day with a mortality percentage of (13.33%), while after one week, with (20.00%) and its highest effectiveness after 28th days of exposure with a mortality percentage of (26.67%). Whilst LGVO, FO, and WCO at a concentration 7.5% had a non-significant impact, they did not register any mortality until the third day, and they remained constant at (6.67%) until the end of the trial.

In the study of the *E. vermiculata* snail, data showed that the (LGVO) at a 30% concentration had a significant

effect after one week, resulting in a mortality percentage of (26.67%). This effect persisted until the end of the trial. In comparison, (FO) and (WCO) had minimal impact, with mortality percentage of 13.33 and 20.00% recorded after 7 and 28 days of exposure, respectively (Table 5). Additionally, it was noted that LGVO, FO, and WCO caused close levels of mortality, with values ranging from 0.00 to 13.33% at various times 1, 3, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days of exposure. Conversely, at a concentration of 7.5%, there was no effect on *E. vermiculata* adults exposed to either FO or WCO, resulting in a mortality percentage of (0.00%). Based on the mean mortality, the (LGVO) oil was found to be the most effective in combating the examined snail species Fig.2. Additionally, the data indicated that adult *M. cartusiana* was more sensitive than *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata*. Hassan *et al.* (2023) mentioned that lemongrass as essential oil has a strong insecticidal activity towards different pest species. These findings can be arranged in order of effectiveness as follows: LGVO > WCO > FO. This variation in effectiveness may be attributed to differences in snail body size.

Table (3): Accretive mortality percentage of *Monacha cartusiana* , adults exposed to vegetable oils.

Tested oils	Conc. %	Accretive mortality / day						
		1 day	3 days	7 days	14 days	21 days	28 days	Mean mortality
FO	7.50	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{ef}	6.67 ^{ef}	6.67 ^{ef}	6.67 ^{ef}	5.56 ^{de}
	15	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{de}	13.33 ^{de}	13.33 ^{de}	13.33 ^{de}	12.22 ^{cd}
	30	13.33 ^b	20.00 ^b	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{cd}	18.98 ^{bc}
WCO	7.50	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{ef}	6.67 ^{ef}	6.67 ^{ef}	6.67 ^{ef}	5.56 ^{de}
	15	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{de}	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{cd}	15.56 ^{cd}
	30	13.33 ^b	20.00 ^b	20.00 ^{cd}	26.67 ^{bc}	26.67 ^{bc}	26.67 ^{bc}	22.22 ^{bc}
LGVO	7.50	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	26.67 ^{bc}	26.67 ^{bc}	26.67 ^{bc}	26.67 ^{bc}	21.11 ^{bc}
	15	13.33 ^b	20.00 ^b	33.33 ^b	33.33 ^b	33.33 ^b	33.33 ^b	27.78 ^b
	30	26.67 ^a	40.00 ^a	53.33 ^a	66.67 ^a	66.67 ^a	66.67 ^a	53.34 ^a
Control	—	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^f	0.00 ^f	0.00 ^f	0.00 ^f	0.00 ^e
P		0.0002 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}
L.S.D. _{0.05}		9.50	10.78	10.77	11.54	11.54	11.54	10.75

- Letters mean the significant differences between treatments, P = Probability, LSD: The least significant difference, and *** very high significant at p<0.001. Fresh oil (FO), Waste cooking oil (WCO) , Lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO).

Table (4): Accretive mortality percentage of *Theba pisana* , adults exposed to vegetable oils.

Tested oils	Conc. %	Accretive mortality / day						
		1 day	3 days	7 days	14 days	21 days	28 days	Mean mortality
FO	7.50	0.00	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{de}	4.45 ^{de}
	15	0.00	0.00 ^c	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{cd}	13.33 ^{cd}	13.33 ^{cd}	8.89 ^{de}
	30	6.67	13.33 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{bc}	20.00 ^{bc}	20.00 ^{bc}	16.67 ^{bc}
WCO	7.50	0.00	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{de}	4.45 ^{de}
	15	0.00	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{bc}	20.00 ^{bc}	12.22 ^{cd}
	30	6.67	13.33 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{bc}	26.67 ^b	26.67 ^b	18.89 ^b
LGVO	7.50	0.00	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{de}	4.45 ^{de}
	15	0.00	13.33 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{ab}	26.67 ^b	26.67 ^b	26.67 ^b	18.89 ^b
	30	6.67	20.00 ^a	26.67 ^a	46.67 ^a	46.67 ^a	46.67 ^a	32.23 ^a
Control	—	0.00	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
P		0.0549 ^{ns}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0011 ^{**}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}
L.S.D. _{0.05}		6.22	8.03	10.77	10.78	10.79	10.79	8.92

-Letters mean the significant differences between treatments, P. = Probability, LSD: The least significant difference, and *** very high significant at p<0.001. Fresh oil (FO), Waste cooking oil (WCO), Lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO).

Table (5): Accretive mortality percentage of *Eobania vermiculata* , adults exposed to vegetable oils.

Tested oils	Conc. %	Accretive mortality / day						
		1 day	3 days	7 days	14 days	21 days	28 days	Mean of mortality
FO	7.50	0.00	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e
	15	0.00	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{cd}	3.34 ^{de}
	30	0.00	0.00 ^c	13.33 ^b	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	8.89 ^{cd}
WCO	7.50	0.00	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e
	15	0.00	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	7.78 ^{cd}
	30	0.00	0.00 ^c	13.33 ^b	20.00 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{ab}	12.22 ^b
LGVO	7.50	0.00	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{bc}	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{cd}	6.67 ^{cd}	4.45 ^{de}
	15	0.00	6.67 ^b	13.33 ^b	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	10.00 ^{bc}
	30	0.00	13.33 ^a	26.67 ^a	26.67 ^a	26.67 ^a	26.67 ^a	20.00 ^a
Control	—	0.00	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e
P		—	0.0002 ^{***}	0.0001 ^{***}				
L.S.D. _{0.05}		—	5.08	8.79	9.49	9.49	9.49	6.63

Letters mean the significant differences between treatments, P. = Probability, LSD: The least significant difference, and *** very high significant at p<0.001. Fresh oil (FO), Waste cooking oil (WCO), Lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO).

Figure (2): Mean mortality of *Monacha cartusiana* , *Theba pisana* , and *Eobania vermiculata* exposed to FO, LGVO, and WCO, as vegetable oils by spraying technique.

3. Biochemical studies: Assaying of digestive enzymes (Amylase and invertas) on examined land snails after exposure to WCO and LGVO oils as vegetable oils:

The data presented in Tables (6, 7 and 8) indicate the impact of WCO and LGVO oils on the vitality of amylase and invertase enzymes in adults of *M. cartusiana*, *T. pisana*, and *E. vermiculata*.

Although LGVO showed a significant stimulatory effect, the inhibitory oils WCO significantly reduced amylase and invertase activity at levels below those of the control throughout the tables. Enzyme activity was significantly reduced by inhibitory treatments in all species, compared to controls (52.72–53.19 and 62.14–63.02 μg glucose/ g b.wt), *M. cartusiana* showed a decrease in amylase to 42.13–46.72 μg glucose/ g b.wt and invertase to 50.42–54.60 μg glucose/ g b.wt at a concentration of 30%. Farag (2020) showed that *Eobaina vermiculata* and *Theba pisana's* invertase activity was decreased by amygdalin isolated from apricot kernels. Amylase and invertase decreased to 38.53–43.17 and 38.16–42.16 μg glucose/ g b. wt, respectively, in *T. pisana* and 36.08–41.55 and 38.74–43.57 μg glucose/ g b. wt, respectively, in *E. vermiculata*. Strongly negative RA% results up to –20.79, –19.31, and –17.63%, which showed a significant reduction of carbohydrates metabolism, supporting these decreases. According to Salbego *et al.* (2014), the organisms' attempt to improve food profiteering in order to make up for other possible food loss caused by poisonous may be the reason for the rise in digestive enzyme

briskness. Notably, at higher concentrations, it led to a slight increase in both enzymes on *E. vermiculata* and *M. cartusiana*. On the other hand, stimulatory oils LGVO significantly increased enzyme activity in all species in a way that was dependent on both time and concentrations; the maximum activation of the studied species was seen in *M. cartusiana*, where amylase rose to 59.43–67.13 μg glucose/ g b.wt., and invertase to 69.14–75.29 μg glucose/ g b.wt. at a concentration of 30%. Amylase and invertase reached 51.39–58.46 and 51.67–55.36 μg glucose/ g b.wt., respectively, in *T. pisana*, and 45.16–49.17 and 51.24–53.12 μg glucose/ g b.wt., respectively in *E. vermiculata*, while RA% values reached 27.04% in *M. cartusiana*, 24.25% in *T. pisana*, and 15.68% in *E. vermiculata*. Establish a high level of metabolic activation; *M. cartusiana* was the most responsive of the examined species, whereas *E. vermiculata* was relatively less activated. Overall, LGVO are used as metabolic promoters, while inhibitory oils WCO are strong inhibitors of digestive enzymes. These various biochemical mechanisms demonstrate their varying potential in molluscicidal strategies, where enzyme inhibitions seem to be more successful in disrupting metabolism. The toxicity of pesticides, which affects the functions of the digestive system in the small intestine, may be the cause of the variation in digestive enzyme activity; this suggestion was made by Khamrakulova (2012).

Table (6): Vitality of amylase and invertase enzymes on adults of *Monacha cartusiana* after exposing to (WCO) and (LGVO) oils by spraying technique.

Tested Oil	Conc. %		Total body homogenates level at the indicated days after treatment of,					
			Amylase			Invertase		
			(µg glucose/ g b.wt.)/days			(µg glucose/ g b.wt.)/days		
			1day	3days	7days	1day	3days	7days
WCO	7.5	SA	44.56 ^e	48.71 ^e	49.33 ^e	58.81 ^e	52.62 ^e	51.88 ^e
		RA%	-16.22	-7.61	-6.64	-5.65	-15.32	-17.68
	15	SA	42.87 ^f	46.02 ^f	48.91 ^f	56.43 ^f	51.93 ^f	51.35 ^f
		RA%	-19.40	-12.71	-7.44	-9.47	-16.43	-18.52
	30	SA	42.13 ^g	45.51 ^g	46.72 ^g	54.60 ^g	51.08 ^g	50.42 ^g
		RA%	-20.79	-13.68	-11.58	-12.40	-17.80	-19.99
LGVO	7.5	SA	56.71 ^c	62.39 ^c	64.22 ^c	71.46 ^c	67.09 ^c	66.85 ^c
		RA%	6.62	18.34	21.54	14.65	7.97	6.08
	15	SA	57.03 ^b	63.48 ^b	64.89 ^b	73.69 ^b	68.82 ^b	67.54 ^b
		RA%	7.22	20.41	22.80	18.23	10.75	7.17
	30	SA	59.43 ^a	65.81 ^a	67.13 ^a	75.29 ^a	71.45 ^a	69.14 ^a
		RA%	11.73	24.83	27.04	20.79	14.98	9.71
Control	—	S A	53.19 ^d	52.72 ^d	52.84 ^d	62.33 ^d	62.14 ^d	63.02 ^d
P			0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***
L.S.D.0.05			0.04	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.03

-SA= Specific activity, -RA %= Relative activity Increase or decrease than control = (treated – control) ÷ control x 100, g. b. w.t = gram body weight, P. = Probability LSD: The least significant difference, ***: very high significant at p<0.001. Waste cooking oil (WCO) , Lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO).

Table (7): Vitality of amylase and invertase enzymes on adults of *Theba pisana* after exposing to (WCO) and (LGVO) oils by spraying technique.

Tested oils	Conc. %		Total body homogenates level at the indicated days after treatment of,					
			Amylase			Invertase		
			1 day	3 days	7 days	1 day	3 days	7 days
			WCO	7.5	SA	39.05 ^e	44.29 ^e	44.78 ^e
RA%	-15.79	-5.73			-4.82	-4.52	-13.26	-15.84
15	SA	38.86 ^f		41.16 ^f	43.89 ^f	44.07 ^f	40.23 ^f	39.09 ^f
	RA%	-16.20		-12.39	-6.72	-4.78	-14.09	-17.34
30	SA	38.53 ^g		41.06 ^g	43.17 ^g	42.16 ^g	38.55 ^g	38.16 ^g
	RA%	-16.91		-12.60	-8.25	-8.90	-17.68	-19.31
LGVO	7.5	SA	48.92 ^c	52.64 ^c	54.62 ^c	52.14 ^c	50.15 ^c	49.74 ^c
		RA%	5.50	12.05	16.09	12.66	7.09	5.18
	15	SA	49.27 ^b	54.82 ^b	56.14 ^b	53.03 ^b	51.72 ^b	50.64 ^b
		RA%	6.25	16.69	19.32	14.59	10.44	7.08
	30	SA	51.39 ^a	56.84 ^a	58.46 ^a	55.36 ^a	53.19 ^a	51.67 ^a
		RA%	10.83	20.99	24.25	19.62	13.58	9.26
Control	—	SA	46.37 ^d	46.98 ^d	47.05 ^d	46.28 ^d	46.83 ^d	47.29 ^d
P			0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***
L.S.D.0.05			0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.06

-SA= Specific activity, -RA %= Relative activity Increase or decrease than control = (treated – control) ÷ control x 100, g. b. w.t = gram body weight, P. = Probability LSD: The least significant difference, ***: very high significant at p<0.001. Waste cooking oil (WCO) , Lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO).

Table (8): Vitality of amylase and invertase enzymes on adults of *Eobania vermiculata* after exposing to (WCO) and (LGVO).

Tested oils	Conc. %		Total body homogenates level at the indicated days after treatment of,					
			Amylase			Invertase		
			1 day	3 days	7 days	1 day	3 days	days
WCO	7.5	S A	38.71 ^e	43.98 ^e	44.93 ^e	44.23 ^e	40.76 ^e	40.07 ^e
		R A %	-10.37	-4.12	-2.43	-3.68	-12.83	-14.80
	15	S A	36.24 ^f	41.17 ^f	43.26 ^f	44.01 ^f	39.83 ^f	39.92 ^f
		R A %	-16.09	-10.25	-6.06	-4.16	-14.82	-15.12
	30	S A	36.08 ^g	39.17 ^g	41.55 ^g	43.57 ^g	38.91 ^g	38.74 ^g
		R A %	-16.46	-14.61	-9.77	-5.12	-16.79	-17.63
LGVO	7.5	S A	44.26 ^c	47.33 ^c	47.79 ^c	50.03 ^c	49.65 ^c	48.98 ^c
		R A %	2.48	3.18	3.78	8.95	6.18	4.15
	15	S A	44.89 ^b	47.91 ^b	48.23 ^b	51.26 ^b	51.34 ^b	50.07 ^b
		R A %	3.94	4.45	4.73	11.63	9.79	6.46
	30	S A	45.16 ^a	48.92 ^a	49.17 ^a	53.12 ^a	52.48 ^a	51.24 ^a
		R A %	4.5	6.65	6.78	15.68	12.23	8.95
Control	—	S A	43.19 ^d	45.87 ^d	46.05 ^d	45.92 ^d	46.76 ^d	47.03 ^d
P			0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***
L.S.D. _{0.05}			0.03	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04

-SA= Specific activity, -RA%= Relative activity Increase or decrease than control = (treated – control) ÷ control x 100, g. b. w.t = gram body weight, P. = Probability LSD: The least significant difference, ***: very high significant at p<0.001. Waste cooking oil (WCO), Lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO).

The study investigated whether lemon grass volatile oil (LGVO) and waste cooking oil (WCO) from used sunflower and soybean oils could increase the mortality rates of *M. cartusiana* and *T. pisana* snails. All treatments revealed that the tested snails' activity for amylase and invertase enzymes treated with WCO decreased, while the same enzymes treated with (LGVO) increased in comparison to the control. The research aims to explore how these enzymes behave under the influence of such combined substances, potentially revealing insights into the physiological effects and adaptive responses of *M. cartusiana* to environmental stressors. By examining the vitality of these enzymes, we hope to understand their roles in metabolic processes and overall health in the presence of industrial waste and natural compounds.

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